

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidative regeneration of carbonyl compounds from oximes by benzyltriethylammonium chlorochromate

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Abstract : The oxidative de-oximation of several aldo- and keto-oximes by benzyltriethylammonium chlorochromate (BTEACC), in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), exhibited a first-order dependence on both the oxime and BTEACC. The oxidation of keto-oximes is slower than that of aldoximes. The rates of oxidation of aldoximes correlated well in terms of Pavelich-Taft dual substituent-parameter equation. The low positive value of polar reaction constant indicated a nucleophilic attack by a chromate-oxygen on the carbon. The reaction is subject to steric hindrance by the alkyl groups. The reaction of acetaldoxime has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect has been analysed by multiparametric equations. A mechanism involving the formation of a cyclic intermediate, in the rate-determining step, has been proposed.

Keywords : Carbonyl compounds, halochromates, correlations.

Regeneration of carbonyl compounds from its derivatives under mild conditions is an important process in synthetic organic chemistry. Several oxidative methods are available for deoximation¹. Halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry². Benzyltriethylammonium chlorochromate (BTEACC) is also one such reagent³. The kinetic and mechanistic aspects of oxidation reactions by BTEACC is scarce in the literature⁴, and in the present communication an attempt has been made in that direction.

Experimental

Materials : Oximes were prepared by the reported methods⁵ and their m.p. were checked with the literature values. BTEACC also was prepared by the reported method³. Solvents were purified by the usual procedure⁶.

Product analysis : The oxidation of the oximes results in the regeneration of corresponding carbonyl compounds, as confirmed by TLC (eluent : CCl₄/Et₂O). Isolation of the product was attempted in the oxidation of oximes of benzaldehyde and acetophenone. In a typical experiment, the oxime (0.2 mol) and BTEACC (0.02 mol) were dissolved in 50 ml of DMSO and allowed to stand for ca. 10 h for the completion of the reaction. Silica gel (5 g) was then added to the reaction mixture and the mixture was stirred for 15 min⁷. It was then filtered and the solid

residue was washed with the solvent (2%; 15 ml). The solvent was removed on a rotary evaporator and the residue was purified on a silica-gel column (eluent : CCl₄/Et₂O). Evaporation of the solvent afforded the pure carbonyl compound. Yields of benzaldehyde and acetophenone were 1.79 g (84%) and 2.13 g (89%) respectively. The presence of HNO₂ in completely reduced reaction mixtures was confirmed by a positive starch-iodide test⁸. The oxidation state of chromium in a completely reduced reaction mixture, as determined by an iodometric method, is 3.90 ± 0.10 .

Kinetics measurements : The reactions were studied under pseudo-first-order conditions by keeping a large excess ($\times 10$ or greater) of the oxime over BTEACC. The solvent was DMSO, unless mentioned otherwise. The reactions were followed at constant temperature by monitoring the decrease in concentration of the BTEACC at 370 nm spectrophotometrically. The pseudo-first-order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear least-squares plots of $\log [\text{BTEACC}]$ versus time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed the rate constants to be reproducible to within $\pm 4\%$. We have used coefficient of determination (R^2 or r^2), standard deviation (sd) and Exner's⁹ parameter, ψ , as the measures of goodness of fit.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry : The analysis of products indicated the

following overall reaction.

The reaction is first-order with respect to BTEACC. The individual kinetic runs yielded linear ($r^2 > 0.995$) plots between $\log [BTEACC]$ and time. Further, the values of k_{obs} do not depend on the initial concentration of BTEACC. The reaction exhibited a linear dependence on the concentration of the oximes (Table 1). The rate constants were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2). The oxidation of acetaldoxime was studied in nineteen different solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of the reactants and the reaction of BTEACC with

primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with chosen solvents. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 3.

The linear correlation ($r^2 = 0.9949$) between the values of the activation parameters of the reaction indicated the operation of a significant compensation effect in this reaction¹⁰. The reaction exhibited an excellent isokinetic effect (temperature 479 ± 13) also, as determined by Exner's method¹¹. An Exner's plot between $\log k_2$ at 288 K and at 318 K is linear ($r^2 = 0.9994$, slope = 0.7739 ± 0.01). The value of isokinetic temperature is 494 ± 15 K. A linear isokinetic relationship is a necessary condition for the validity of linear free energy relationships. It also implies that all reactions so correlated follow a similar mechanism⁹.

The rate constants, k_2 , of the oxidation of acetaldoxime in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship [eq. (2)] of Kamlet *et al.*¹²

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + \alpha \quad (2)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (2), a bi-parametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below [eqs. (3)-(6)].

$$\begin{aligned} \log k_2 = -3.92 + 2.03 (\pm 0.19) \pi^* + \\ 0.16 (\pm 0.16) \beta + 0.44 (\pm 0.15) \alpha \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

$$R^2 = 0.8999; sd = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.35$$

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of acetaldoxime by BTEACC at 298 K

$10^3 [BTEACC]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Oxime] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.1	16.2
1.0	0.2	31.5
1.0	0.3	63.0
1.0	0.5	96.3
1.0	0.8	126
1.0	1.0	159
1.0	1.5	243
0.5	0.8	64.9
2.0	0.8	64.5
3.0	0.8	63.5
4.0	0.8	64.2
5.0	0.8	65.0

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of oximes ($R^1 R^2 C=N-OH$) by BTEACC

Substituent		$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^*	ΔS^*	ΔG^*
		288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K	(kJ mol ⁻¹)	(J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	(kJ mol ⁻¹)
H	H	2520	3110	3590	3960	10.0 ± 0.7	-225 ± 2	76.0 ± 0.6
H	Me	106	159	234	316	24.8 ± 0.5	-197 ± 2	83.3 ± 0.4
H	Et	81.0	126	187	259	27.1 ± 0.5	-191 ± 2	83.9 ± 0.4
H	Pr	43.2	69.3	108	158	30.5 ± 0.3	-185 ± 1	85.3 ± 0.2
H	Pr ⁱ	31.5	51.3	82.8	126	32.8 ± 0.2	-179 ± 1	86.1 ± 0.1
H	ClCH ₂	234	317	418	504	17.2 ± 0.7	-217 ± 2	81.6 ± 0.5
H	Ph	207	319	486	765	30.5 ± 0.6	-172 ± 2	81.5 ± 0.5
Me	Me	4.41	8.19	15.3	27.0	43.6 ± 0.3	-158 ± 1	90.6 ± 0.2
Me	Et	3.37	6.39	12.2	22.1	45.4 ± 0.4	-154 ± 1	91.2 ± 0.3
Et	Et	2.57	4.99	9.76	18.0	47.0 ± 0.4	-151 ± 1	91.8 ± 0.3
Me	Ph	18.9	26.1	36.9	51.3	22.9 ± 0.4	-218 ± 2	87.7 ± 0.4

Note

$$\log k_2 = -3.97 + 1.87 (\pm 0.23) \pi^* + 0.31 (\pm 0.19) \beta \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8405; sd = 0.22; n = 18; \psi = 0.432$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.91 + 1.95 (\pm 0.24) \pi^* \quad (5)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8108; sd = 0.23; n = 18; \psi = 0.45$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.88 + 0.65 (\pm 0.41) \beta \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1329; sd = 0.49; n = 18; \psi = 0.96$$

Kamlet's triparametric equation explains *ca.* 90% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion the correlation is not even satisfactory [cf. eq. (3)]. The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 84% of the data. Both β and α play

$$\log k_2 = 1.69 (\pm 0.29) B - 3.78 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.6719; sd = 0.32; n = 19; \psi = 0.59$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.75 \pm 0.03 (A + B) - 3.70 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9944; sd = 0.04; n = 19; \psi = 0.08$$

The rates of oxidation of acetaldoxime in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation [cf. eq. (8)] with both the anion- and cation-solvating powers playing almost equal role. However, individually *A* and *B* are able to account for only 23 and 67% of the data only. The solvent polarity, represented by (*A* + *B*), also exhibited an excellent correlation. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 99% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not very significant ($r^2 = 0.4769; sd = 0.40; \psi = 0.74$).

Correlation analysis of reactivity : The reaction of alkenes with chromium(VI) has been well studied¹⁴. Since, olefinic bonds are not usually subject to a nucleophilic attack, it has been suggested that in the alkene-chromate reaction, an organometallic derivative is formed initially. The organometallic derivative then changes to a chromium(IV) diester in the rate-determining step. However, carbon-nitrogen double bonds, being dipolar in nature, can be easily attacked by a nucleophile. The data in Table 2 showed that the rate of oxidation of ketoximes is much less as compared to that of the aldoximes. The reason for the slower reaction of ketoximes must be steric. As the central carbon changes from a trigonal to a tetragonal state, the crowding around it increases. This increase in the steric crowding will be more in the case of ketoximes as compared to that in aldoximes. This observation is supported by the correlation analysis of the reactivity of the aldoximes also. The rate of oxidation of the aliphatic oximes did not yield significant correlation separately with Taft's σ^* and E_s values [eqs. (12) and (13)]. The rates were, therefore, correlated with Pavelich-Taft's¹⁵ dual substituent-parameter [eq. (14)].

$$\log k_2 = 0.81 \pm 0.52 \sigma^* - 1.85 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.3839; sd = 0.56; n = 6; \psi = 0.83; \text{temp.} = 298 \text{ K}$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.97 \pm 0.18 E_s - 1.71 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8817; sd = 0.25; n = 6; \psi = 0.36; \text{temp.} = 298 \text{ K}$$

$$\log k_2 = \rho^* \sigma^* + \delta E_s + \log k_0 \quad (14)$$

Table 3. Effect of solvent on the oxidation of acetaldoxime by BTEACC at 298 K

Solvent	$10^4 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	Solvent	$10^4 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
Chloroform	51.3	Toluene	7.41
1,2-Dichloroethane	43.7	Acetophenone	53.7
Dichloromethane	47.9	Tetrahydrofuran	14.8
DMSO	159	<i>t</i> -BuOH	22.4
Acetone	33.9	Dioxane	18.2
Dimethylformamide	77.6	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	9.77
Butanone	24.0	Acetic acid	26.9
Nitrobenzene	57.5	Ethyl acetate	12.3
Benzene	10.2	Carbon disulfide	3.47
Cyclohexane	0.69		

relatively minor roles. The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation¹³ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also [eq. (7)].

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (7)$$

Here *A* represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and *B* the cation-solvating power. *C* is the intercept term. (*A* + *B*) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (7), separately with *A* and *B* and with (*A* + *B*).

$$\log k_2 = 1.62 (\pm 0.03) A + 1.82 (\pm 0.02) B - 3.70 \quad (8)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9979; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.05$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.36 (\pm 0.60) A - 3.06 \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.2328; sd = 0.48; n = 19; \psi = 0.89$$

Table 4. Reaction constants for the oxidative deoxygenation of aliphatic aldoximes by BTEACC^a

Temp. (K)	ρ^*	δ	R^2	sd	ψ
288	0.54 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.02	0.9999	0.001	0.011
298	0.48 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.01	0.9989	0.002	0.038
308	0.42 ± 0.01	0.79 ± 0.01	0.9998	0.001	0.016
318	0.35 ± 0.02	0.73 ± 0.01	0.9999	0.007	0.011

^aNumber of compounds is 6.

The rates exhibited excellent correlations in terms of the Pavelich-Taft equation (Table 4); the reaction constants are being positive.

Mechanism :

The low positive polar reaction constant points to an almost cyclic transition state in which the formation of the bond between chromate-oxygen and the carbon is somewhat ahead of the formation of N-O bond. This supports a nucleophilic attack by a chromate-oxygen on the carbon. The positive steric reaction constant points to a steric hindrance by the substituents. Therefore, the following mechanism (Scheme 1) is proposed for the reaction. The mechanism is supported by the values of activation parameters also. The low values of enthalpy of activation indicate that the bond-cleavage and bond-formation are almost synchronous. The large negative entropies of activation support the formation of a rigid cyclic activated complex from two acyclic molecules.

Scheme 1

Hydroxynitrene (N-OH) has been recently reported as a very reactive intermediate.

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